

Figures:

Figure 1. Pillars of entrepreneurial ecosystem

Source: Own elaboration based on the GEI (2019), data from the Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute

Figure 2. Evolution of liberal democracy Eastern Europe

Source: Own elaboration based on the data about liberal democracy from the V-Dem Institute

Tables:

Table 1. List of countries under analysis for the TFP model

Austria	Denmark	Ireland	Portugal
Belgium	Spain	Italy	Romania
Bulgaria	Estonia	Lithuania	Slovakia
Cyprus	Finland	Latvia	Slovenia
Czechia	France	Netherlands	Sweden
Germany	Hungary	Poland	

Table 2. The empirical model applied on the Eastern European Countries (Poland, Czechia, Romania, Hungary, Slovakia, Bulgaria)

<i>Dependent variable:</i>					
	TFP				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
TCI (normalized)	0.007 (0.014)	-0.005 (0.010)	-0.004 (0.016)		
log (GDPINC)		-2.812*** (0.549)	-3.129** (0.834)	-4.544 (3.192)	
log (Population)			-10.900 (9.611)	-53.764** (20.557)	
GEI (normalized)				0.015 (0.020)	
ECI (normalized)					-0.051**

					(0.018)
log (Diversity)					-2.225*** (0.449)
log (FDI)					0.521 (0.499)

Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	118	118	118	57	111
R ²	0.075	0.310	0.317	0.213	0.241
Adjusted R ²	0.025	0.266	0.266	0.082	0.182
Residual Std. Error	2.760 (df = 111)	2.395 (df = 110)	2.394 (df = 109)	2.077 (df = 48)	2.520 (df = 102)

Note:

* p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Table 3. The empirical model with country clustered standard error.

<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	TFP			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
TCI (normalized)	-0.034** (0.015)	0.022** (0.011)	0.025* (0.014)	
log (GDPINC)		-2.456*** (0.473)	-2.485*** (0.463)	
log (Population)			3.905 (3.801)	
ECI (normalized)				-0.070*** (0.025)

log (Diversity)	-0.671*
	(0.349)
log (FDI)	0.050
	(0.111)

Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robust SE: Cluster	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	543	543	543	505
R ²	0.181	0.302	0.306	0.286
Adjusted R ²	0.145	0.270	0.272	0.249
Residual Std. Error	2.654 (df = 519)	2.453 (df = 518)	2.449 (df = 517)	2.468 (df = 479)

Note:

* p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Table 4. The empirical model testing the relationship between the complexity gap and liberal democracy.

Regression Models

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>			
	Liberal Democracy			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Log (FDI)	-0.013			
	(0.010)			

ECI (normalized)	-0.627**			
	(0.242)			
TCI (normalized)		0.142		
		(0.122)		
Complexity Gap (Standardized)				-0.250**
				(0.111)
log (GDP/cap)				0.063
				(0.047)

Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	167	175	175	175
R ²	0.678	0.653	0.640	0.653
Adjusted R ²	0.604	0.578	0.563	0.575
Residual Std. Error	0.087	0.090	0.092	0.091
	(df = 135)	(df = 143)	(df = 143)	(df = 142)

Source: Own elaboration

*p<0.1;

>** p<0.05; >*** p<0.01

Sample: Slovenia, Czechia, Romania, Hungary, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Croatia

Note: The complexity gap was calculated by normalizing the ECI and TCI scores and subtracting the TCI from the ECI and then standardizing the difference, this was done for each country and each year. The data on early liberal democracy were obtained from the V-dem Institute. The institute's description of the index is as follows: The liberal principle of democracy emphasizes the importance of protecting individual and minority rights against the tyranny of the state and the tyranny of the majority. The liberal model takes a "negative" view of political power, judging the

quality of democracy by the limits placed on government. This is achieved through constitutionally protected civil liberties, a strong rule of law, an independent judiciary, and effective checks and balances that together limit the exercise of executive power. To make this a measure of liberal democracy, the index also takes into account the level of electoral democracy (Coppedge, Michael, John Gerring, Carl Henrik Knutsen, Staffan I. Lindberg, Jan Teorell, David Altman, Michael Bernhard, Agnes Cornell, M. Steven Fish, Lisa Gastaldi, Haakon Gjerløw, Adam Glynn, Sandra Grahn, Allen Hicken, Katrin Kinzelbach, Kyle L. Marquardt, Kelly McMann, Valeriya Mechkova, Anja Neundorf, Pamela Paxton, Daniel Pemstein, Oskar Rydén, Johannes von Römer, Brigitte Seim, Rachel Sigman, Svend-Erik Skaaning, Jeffrey Staton, Aksel Sundström, Eitan Tzelgov, Luca Uberti, Yi-ting Wang, Tore Wig, and Daniel Ziblatt. 2023. "V-Dem Codebook v13" Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) Project.).

Table 5. Causality tests between the Complexity Gap and Liberal Democracy

No	Test	Model	Ztilde	P-Value	Alternative Hypothesis
1	Granger Test 1	Complexity Gap granger cause Liberal Democracy	-0.67744921	0.4981210	Granger causality for at least one individual
2	Granger Test 2	Liberal Democracy granger cause Complexity Gap	-0.01144729	0.9908666	Granger causality for at least one individual